

Effect of apical pinching on Okra

**Bhakti Panchal¹, D. R. Bhanderi²
and R. V. Tank³**

ISSN: 1542-2666
NAAS Rating (2025): 5.00
<https://www.jarvm.co/index.html>
jarvm.submit@gmail.com
2025; 20-1(Part-B): 96-101

Received: 15-08-2025
Accepted: 08-09-2025

Bhakti Panchal
Scientist-Horticulture, KVK,
NAU, Surat, Gujarat
D. R. Bhanderi
Professor and Head,
Department of Vege. Sci.,
ACH, NAU, Navsari, Gujarat
Associate professor, **R. V.
Tank**
Department of Fruit Sci., ACH,
NAU, Navsari, Gujarat

Corresponding Author:

Bhakti Panchal
Scientist-Horticulture, KVK,
NAU, Surat, Gujarat

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17078826

Abstract:

The present investigation effect of apical pinching on growth and yield of okra was carried out at Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Navsari Agricultural University, Surat (Gujarat) during *Kharif*- 2022 and 2023. The experiment was conducted in Randomized Block Design in Factorial concept with three replications. Significantly maximum number of branches per plant (2.29), plant height (26.65, 33.15, 47.33, 54.06 and 61.53 cm at 30, 45, 60, 75 and 90 DAS, respectively), leaf area per plant (909.55 cm²), number of nodes per plant (14.71), maximum number of pods per plant (14.14), yield per plant (175.16 g) and pod weight (12.01 g) were obtained with the treatment T4- apical pinching at fifty days after sowing in growth and yield characters. While, days to first flowering, days to 50 % flowering, number of leaves per plant (0-90 DAS), days to first picking and days to last picking were found non-significant with all four levels of apical pinching.

Key-word: Apical pinching, Okra, yield, pods per plant

Introduction:

Okra [*Abelmoschus esculentus* (L.) Moench], a member of the Malvaceae family, is an annual fruit vegetable crop and having chromosome no. 2n=130, has captured a prominent position among vegetables. Okra is commonly referred to as *Gumbo* in the US, lady's finger in the UK, *Bhindi* in India and *Bhinda* in Gujarat. The crop was originated from Tropical Africa and first cultivated by the Egyptians in the 12th AD (Thompson and Kelly, 1979). It is widely grown throughout the world's tropical and subtropical regions. It is popular among vegetable growers throughout India due to adaptability to a wide range of growing conditions. Apical pinching is one of the crucial and recently practised agro techniques in okra, which has a direct correlation

on yield. Apical pinching now a day's increasing attention in vegetable crops particularly in tomato, okra and cucurbitaceous crops. Apical pinching mostly decreases apical dominance there by arrests the vertical growth and hastens the growth of productive branches (Kabir, 2010). The physiology behind this operation is to alter the source sink relationship by curbing the vegetative growth thus it increases the photosynthetic activities, accumulation of photosynthates, fruit formation, fruit production and yield (Lakshmi, *et al.*, 2015). Apical pinching promotes lateral branches, increasing flowering sites, improves canopy structure and overall increasing the production in okra. It is important to note that the timing and method of pinching can influence the outcome and some

studies have shown mixed results regarding yield increases in okra.

Material and Methods:

The present investigation was carried out at Krishi Vigyan Kendra, NAU, Surat (Gujarat, India). Geographically Surat is situated on the bank of the perennial river Tapi which flow into the Arabian ocean. The location of Surat is 21°15' N Latitude and 72°52' E Longitude. The Arabian Sea is to its west at a distance of about 22 kilometres along the Tapi and about 16 kilometres by road. The experiment was conducted in Randomized Block Design in Factorial concept with three replications. According to treatment of the growth retardation methods apical pinching was done by removing small portion of main shoot (growing tip of the main stem) by cutter at 30, 40 and 50 days after sowing. Treatment combinations were T1: No apical pinching, T2: apical pinching at 30 DAS, T3: apical pinching at 40 DAS and T4: apical pinching at 50 DAS.

Results and Discussion:

Different timings of apical pinching had significant effect on number of branches per plant during both experimental years. Recorded maximum number of branches per plant was in P4- apical pinching 50 DAS during the both years (2.94 and 3.05 in the year 2022, 2023, respectively). Which was statistically at par with the treatments P2- apical pinching at 30 days after sowing (2.84 and 2.90 in the year 2022, 2023, respectively). Increase in number of branches may be due to suppression of vertical growth resulting in translocation of

photosynthates to leaf axil thus encouraging the lateral branches. Due to repetitive removal of portion of main branch, axillary buds become free from correlative inhibition of apical dominance and started growing. This resulted into more branching and spread of plants Feroz *et al.* (2010). Maximum leaf area per plant was recorded in P4- apical pinching @ 50 DAS (909.11 cm² and 910.00 cm² in the year 2022, 2023, respectively) and none of the treatments statistically at par with it in both years also. While, the minimum leaf area per plant recorded in P1- no apical pinching (882.25 cm² and 876.03 cm² in the year 2022 and 2023, respectively) in okra. Upon removal of the terminal bud, apical dominance is removed, resulting in lateral bud growth through an auxin-mediated process (Patil *et al.* 2012) which increases branches. Even though the leaves were small in case of pruned treatments the overall leaf area was recorded highest in case of pruned treatments only. Similar opinions were expressed by Sanodiya *et al.* (2017), Sahu and Biswal (2017), Baraskar *et al.* (2018) and Muhammad *et al.* (2019). The highest number of nodes per main shoot was recorded in P4- apical pinching at 50 days after sowing (14.55 and 14.86 in the year 2022, 2023, respectively) which was statistically at par with treatments P3- apical pinching at 40 DAS (13.26 and 14.40 in the year 2022, 2023, respectively). While, the less number of nodes per main shoot recorded in P2- apical pinching @ 30 DAS (12.60 and 13.73 in the year 2022, 2023, respectively) in okra.

Table 1: Effect of apical pinching on number of branches per plant, leaf area per plant (cm²) and number of nodes per main shoot in okra

Treatments	Number of branches per plant		Leaf area per plant (cm ²)		Number of nodes per main shoot	
	2022	2023	2022	2023	2022	2023
P1	2.56 ^b	2.84 ^a	882.25 ^c	876.03 ^c	12.73 ^b	14.33 ^a
P2	2.84 ^{ab}	2.90 ^a	893.57 ^{bc}	893.08 ^b	12.60 ^b	13.73 ^a
P3	2.74 ^{ab}	2.88 ^a	902.35 ^{ab}	899.04 ^b	13.26 ^{ab}	14.40 ^a
P4	2.94 ^a	3.05 ^a	909.11 ^a	910.00 ^a	14.55 ^a	14.86 ^a
SEm (±)	0.11	0.09	4.07	3.57	0.50	0.43
CD at 5%	0.31	0.26	11.66	10.24	1.45	1.25
CV (%)	15.37	12.04	1.75	1.54	14.76	11.83

The maximum plant height (26.65, 33.15, 47.33, 54.06 and 61.53 cm at 30, 45, 60, 75 and 90 DAS, respectively). Pruning significantly reduces plant height due to the action of apical de-budding when compared with the control plants. It might be related to the flow of auxin in the plants, the synthesis of auxin on the shoot of the main stem is stopped due to the shoot pruning, while the synthesis of cytokinin increased and further affected the growth of branches Naruka and Paliwal (2000). Kokare *et al.* (2006) reported that pruning suppresses apical dominance. The above results are in line with the findings of Surendra *et al.* (2006), Aikins *et al.* (2017), Rahman *et al.* (2016) and Tswanya and Olaniyi (2016) in tomato, Mardhiana *et al.* (2017).

Table 2: Effect of apical pinching on plant height (cm) in okra

Treatments	Plant height (cm)									
	2022					2023				
	30 DAS	45 DAS	60 DAS	75 DAS	90 DAS	30 DAS	45 DAS	60 DAS	75 DAS	90 DAS
P1	25.30 ^a	32.06 ^{ab}	45.93 ^a	53.46 ^a	60.06 ^a	25.49 ^b	31.75 ^b	48.73 ^a	54.66 ^a	62.96^a
P2	25.36 ^a	32.04 ^b	44.86 ^a	52.33 ^{ab}	58.73 ^a	25.93 ^{ab}	32.01 ^b	48.93 ^a	54.13 ^a	62.86^a
P3	25.03 ^a	31.96 ^b	44.26 ^a	50.74 ^b	58.40 ^a	25.29 ^b	32.26 ^{ab}	48.00 ^a	54.46 ^a	63.86^a
P4	25.23 ^a	33.28 ^a	44.73 ^a	51.60 ^{ab}	58.46 ^a	26.20 ^a	33.02 ^a	49.93 ^a	55.86 ^a	64.60^a
SEm (±)	0.24	0.44	0.85	0.79	0.94	0.24	0.48	0.89	1.18	1.23
CD at 5%	0.70	1.27	2.43	2.27	2.71	0.69	1.39	2.56	3.38	3.53
CV (%)	3.80	5.37	7.32	5.92	6.23	3.66	5.87	7.09	8.35	7.51

An appraisal of result indicated that maximum number of pods per plant was recorded in P4- apical pinching at 50 days after sowing (14.48 and 13.80 in the year 2022, 2023, respectively) which was statistically at par with P2- apical pinching at 30 DAS (13.47 and 13.76 in the year 2022, 2023, respectively). While, the minimum number of pods per plant recorded in P1- no apical pinching (12.98 and 12.78 in the year 2022, 2023, respectively) in okra and the highest pod yield per plant (g) was recorded in P4- apical pinching at 50 days after sowing (176.35 g and 173.96 g in the year 2022, 2023, respectively) which was statistically at par with treatment P3- apical pinching at 40 DAS (162.29 g and 163.14 g in the year 2022, 2023, respectively). While, the lowest pod yield per plant recorded in P1- no apical pinching (156.77 g and 160.23 g in the experimental year 2022, 2023, respectively). Apical pinching helps in the production of more side branches, resulting in increased photosynthetic activity and accumulation of photosynthates, ultimately resulting in increased yield (Olasantan, 1986). Basically, pruning is intended to control the optimal number of leaves thereby improving the yield. Pruning is an attempt to create a better state of the plant, so that sunlight can enter to the whole parts of the plant, increase interception of light into the canopy of plants and increase the availability of air circulation and CO₂ in the canopy. The sufficient light, CO₂ and other supporting factors will increase the photosynthesis rate which leads to increase the availability of photosynthesis. The excessive vegetative growth caused a suboptimal use of photosynthesis results and led to decrease the yield production. Hence pruning facilitates opening of leaves to sunlight and prevent shading, partitioning of assimilates was high in pruned plants and therefore more pods were produced. Similar results were obtained by Sarkar *et al.* (2007), Olasantan and Salau (2008), Feroz *et al.* (2010), Aliyu *et al.* (2015), Rahman *et al.* (2016), Ahmad *et al.* (2016), Sowmya *et al.* (2017), Aikins *et al.* (2017) and Ali *et al.* (2021). Apical bud pinching made a way out to produce more branches. As in case of okra except below 2-3 nodes all above nodes produce fruits hence this increase in branches might have led to the increase in number of fruits. These results are in accordance with Marie *et al.* (2007), Olasantan and Salau (2008), Kabir (2007), Aliyu *et al.* (2015), Sahu and Biswal (2017) in okra. Similar opinions were made by Maity *et al.* (2016). Increase in photosynthetic activity produces more carbohydrates which directly influenced the fruit size, number of fruit and ultimately final yield. Choudhury *et al.*

(2014) reported that foliar application of GA₃ was highly efficient in production and translocation of assimilates to the developing sink in cowpea. Significantly highest pod weight was recorded in P4-apical pinching @ 50 DAS (12.08 g in the year 2022) which was statistically at par with treatment P1-no apical pinching (11.91 g in the year 2022). While the minimum pod weight recorded in P2- apical pinching @ 30 DAS (11.81 g during year 2022) in okra.

Table 3: Effect of apical pinching on number of pods per plant, pod yield per plant (g) and pod weight (g) in okra

Treatments	Number of pods per plant		Pod yield per plant (g)		Pod weight (g)	
	2022	2023	2022	2023	2022	2023
P1	12.98 ^b	12.78 ^b	156.77 ^b	160.23 ^b	11.91 ^a	11.89 ^a
P2	13.47 ^a	13.76 ^a	159.81 ^{ab}	164.34 ^{ab}	11.80 ^a	11.82 ^a
P3	13.42 ^{ab}	13.67 ^{ab}	162.29 ^{ab}	163.14 ^{ab}	11.66 ^a	12.06 ^a
P4	14.48 ^a	13.80 ^a	176.35 ^a	173.96 ^a	12.08 ^a	11.94 ^a
SEm (±)	0.40	0.41	4.98	5.36	0.15	0.16
CD at 5%	1.14	1.18	14.07	15.36	0.45	0.48
CV (%)	11.22	11.52	11.71	12.67	5.19	5.47

Conclusion:

From the two years study it can be concluded that in okra apical pinching done at 50 days after sowing resulted in better growth and yield of plants. Maximum internodal length per plant (5.56 cm), number of branches per plant (2.99), plant height (26.65, 33.15, 47.33, 54.06 and 61.53 cm at 30, 45, 60, 75 and 90 DAS, respectively), leaf area per plant (909.55 cm²), number of nodes per plant (14.71), number of pods per plant (14.14), yield per plant (175.16 g) and pod weight (12.01 g) were recorded in growth characters. While, days to first flowering, days to 50 % flowering, number of leaves per plant (0-90 DAS), days to first picking and days to last picking were found non-significant with all four levels of apical pinching.

References:

- Ahmad, N.; Abdur, R.; Muhammad, S.; Zahid, A. and Kawsar, A. (2016). Influence of pinching intensity and incremental nitrogen application on growth and yield of okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* L. Moench). *International Journal of Agriculture Environment Research*, **2** (1): 77-85.
- Aikins, K. A.; Najombu, T. And Msibi, S.T. (2017). Effect of apical pinching on the performance of Asontem okra. *Western Journal of Agriculture Science*, **13** (2): 68-74.
- Ali, A.; Muhammad, I. N.; Khan, M. N.; Muhammad, I.; Ali, S.; Rehman, J. and Ali, W. (2021). Pinching effects on growth and yield of okra. *Pure and Applied Biology*, **11** (1):135- 145.
- Aliyu, U.; Sukuni, M. and Abubakar, L. (2015). Effect of pruning on growth and fresh fruit yield of okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* L.) in Sokota, Nigeria. *Journal of Global Bioscience*, **4** (7): 2636-2640.
- Baraskar, T. V.; Gawande, P. P.; Kayande, N. V.; Lande, S. S. and Naware, M. S. (2018). Effect of plant growth regulators on growth parameters of okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* L. Moench). *International Journal of Chemical Studies*, **6** (6): 165-68.
- Chowdhury, M. S.; Hasan, Z.; Kabir, K.; Shah Jahan, M. and Kabir, M. H. (2014). Response of okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* L.) to growth regulators and organic manures. *The Agriculture*, **12** (2): 56-63.
- Feroz, Z. A.; Nasiruddin, K. M.; Mondal, M. and Farooq, A. (2010). Growth and yield of okra as influenced by hill elevation and plant de-topping in hill slope

- condition. *Bangladesh Journal of Agricultural Research*, **35** (2): 355-58.
8. Kabir, A. (2010). Effect of branch pruning on plant growth, fruit and seed yield in okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus*) cultivar (Nao 47-4 and LD88-1). Unpublished research project submitted to crop production department, Federal University of Technology, Minna, Niger State: 18.
 9. Kokare, R.T.; Bhalerao, R.K.; Prabu, T.; Chavan, S. K.; Bansode, A. B. and Kachare, G. S. (2006). Effect of plant growth regulators on growth, yield and quality of okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* (L.) Moench). *Agriculture Science Digest*, **26** (3): 178-181.
 10. Lakshmi, J.; Gowda, R.; Parashivamurthy, N. S. and V. N. Shivanandam (2015). Influence of pre-flowering pinching and maleic hydrazide spray on plant growth, seed yield and quality attributes in fenugreek. *Legume Research*, **38** (3): 353-357.
 11. Maity, U.; Dutta, P. and Layek, B. (2016). Effect of plant growth regulators on growth, yield and quality of okra [*Abelmoschus esculentus* (L.) Moench]. *Journal of Agronomic Natural Resource Management*, **3** (3):251-253.
 12. Mardhiana, M.; Pradana, A. P.; Adiwena, M.; Kartina, K.; Santoso, D.; Wijaya, R. and Maliki, A. (2017). Effects of pruning on growth and yield of cucumber (*Cucumis sativus*) Mercy variety in the acid soil of North Kalimantan, Indonesia. *Cell Biology Development*, **1** (1): 13-17.
 13. Marie, A. I.; Ihsan, A. and Salih, S. H. (2007). Effects of sowing date, topping and some growth regulators on growth, pod and seeds yield of okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* (L.) Moench). "African Crop Science Conference Proceeding". **8**: 473-478.
 14. Muhammad, T. T.; Muhammad, A. A.; Muhammad, S.; Muhammad, F. K. and Sajjad, H. (2019). Seed priming and foliar application of plant growth regulators affect the growth and yield of okra under calcareous soils. *Acta Scientiarum Polonorum Hortorum Cultus*, **18** (4):25–33.
 15. Naruka, I. S. and Paliwal, R. (2000). Ameliorative potential of gibberelic acid and NAA on growth and yield attributes of Okra. *South Indian Journal of Horticulture*, **48** (1-6): 129-131.
 16. Olasantan, F. O. (1986). Effect of apical de-budding on growth and yield of okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus*). *Experimental Agriculture*, **22** (3): 307-12.
 17. Olasantan, F. O. and Salau A. W. (2008). Effect of pruning on growth, leaf yield and pod yield of okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* (L.) Moench). *Journal of Agricultural Science*, **146** (1): 93-102.
 18. Patil, S.W.; Aher, B. M.; Sakure, A. A. and Dahake, A. B. (2012). Apical bud pinching in Okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus*): A review. *Seed Technology*, 139-144.
 19. Rahman, N. T.; Ali, S.; Rahman, I.; Muhammad, A.; Muhammad I.; Nauman, S. and Irshad, A. (2016). Effect of seed priming and pinching on growth parameters of okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* L.). *Pure and Applied Biology*, **5** (1): 165-171.
 20. Sahu, Priyanka and Biswal, Monalisha (2017). Effect of pinching treatments on growth, flowering and yield of okra cv. Pusa A4. *Trends in Bioscience*, **10** (17): 3089-3092.
 21. Sanodiya, K.; Pandey, G.; Kacholli, P. and Dubey, A. K. (2017). Effect of growth regulator on growth, yield and seed quality parameters of okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* L.): cv. Utkal Gaurav. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Science*, **6** (10): 3551-3556.
 22. Sarkar, R. K.; Datta, S. and Jana, J. C. (2007). Effect of pinching on chilli (*Capsicum annum*).
 - a. *Indian Journal of Agriculture Science*, **77** (12): 856-858.
 23. Sowmya, P. T.; Naruka, I. S.; Shaktawat,

- R. P. S. and Kushwah, S. S. (2017). Effect of sowing dates and stage of pinching on growth, yield and quality of fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum-graecum* L.). *International Journal of Bio-resources and Stress Management*, **8** (1): 91-95.
24. Surendra, P.; Nawalagatti, C. M.; Chetti, M. B. and Hiremath, S. M. (2006). Effect of plant growth regulators and micronutrients on morpho-physiological and biochemical traits and yield in okra. *Karnataka Journal of Agriculture Science*, **19** (3): 694-697.
25. Thompson, H. C. and Kelly, W. C. (1979). "Vegetable Crops". Me Grow Hill Co. New York, pp. 562.
26. Tswana, N. M. and Olaniyi, O. J. (2016). Effects of pinching time on growth and fruit yield of three tomato varieties (*Lycopersicon esculentum* mill) in the southern guinea savanna zone of Nigeria. *International Journal of Agriculture*, **1** (1): 30-40.